

FIBER DISTRIBUTION AND RESIN FLOW IN THE LAMINATE MOLDING PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

Consolidation and cure experiments on flat graphite/epoxy laminate composites were designed and conducted for the purpose of simulating the micro-structure development during the bleeder molding process. The Hercules AS4/3501-6 prepreg tapes with 50% initial fiber volume fraction were used in the experiments. Very thin and teflon coated glass fabric sheets with large porosity were impregnated between the prepreg layers in the lay-up operation in order to monitor the fiber volume fraction and the resin content for each ply and at the same time to keep the flow field undisturbed. Special temperature and pressure cycles were selected to obtain certain time windows in the process to observe the micro-structure developments. The process was also simulated by using computer program based on Gutowski's fiber deformation/resin flow model [1], in which the fiber network was treated as a nonlinear elastic porous medium and the resin flow was assumed to obey Darcy's law. The experiment results verified the model predictions and revealed the micro-structure development of the composites.

INTRODUCTION

In the processing of advanced thermoset composites, high fiber volume fraction is achieved by applying pressure to the laminate to squeeze out the excess resin. For large size composite laminate structure, bleeder material was used with the laminate to induce the transverse resin flow. The compaction behavior of the composite laminate during the consolidation and cure process is fundamental to the determination of the optimal cure cycle, which is critical to the final quality of the composite parts. The mechanism of the compaction, which includes the resin flow and fiber movement, has been discussed in several papers and models were constructed to describe the consolidation process [1, 2, 3, 4]. Various simulation experiments were performed to investigate the process mechanisms. The direct continuous measurement of the laminate compaction, in which the total laminate thickness was monitored as a function of process time, was reported in a recent paper [5]. However, the micro-structure development of the composite laminate during this consolidation process, such as the fiber motion and the resin content within the structure, was still not fully understood, especially in the bleeder molding case where the transverse resin flow was dominant. The objective of this work, therefore, is to provide an alternative way of monitoring the micro-structure development of the composite laminate as a function of process time. This measurement would make a better understanding of the compaction mechanism and help to determine the optimal cure cycle.

EXPERIMENTS

The key issues in this experiment were to select a special cure cycle to obtain an incomplete resin flow state, and to impregnate non-stick porous teflon coated sheets within the structure so that changes of individual ply could be measured

weld. The ply thickness of the composite material used was about 0.15 mm (0.006 inch). It was impossible to place an individual ply to monitor the micro-structure development with the flow field because of the available sensor size. The study of resin viscosity change revealed that during the cure process, the viscosity decreased to a minimum point then increased rapidly until the resin was cured. This special resin property required the selection of the pressure cycle to obtain the certain resin flow time period. In this experiment, we utilize this resin viscosity property and designed a set of special pressure and temperature cycle so that we could simulate the cure process but "freeze" the resin flow states corresponding to different time windows. In other words, we intentionally obtained incomplete compaction of the specimen then measured the micro-structure development as a function of time.

The material used in these experiments was graphite/epoxy composite material AS4/3501-6. The prepreg tape was supplied by Hercules Inc. The initial resin content of the prepreg was about 50% in volume fraction. The uncompacted thickness of the prepreg was about 0.18 mm (0.007 in). The viscosity of the this kind of resin was studied by Springer in [6] and was found to be a function of temperature and time. Fig. 1 shows the viscosity change in a certain temperature cycle, which is calculated according to the formula given in [6]. The viscosity decreases as temperature rises and reaches a minimum point. Then it increases rapidly when the cure reaction progresses. Usually pressure is applied before this minimum resin viscosity point in order to obtain a full compaction. In our experiments, however, we applied the pressure after this minimum point was passed. Therefore the rapidly increased resin viscosity stopped flow of the resin at a certain time. In this way we can obtain a "frozen" flow field with some kind of incomplete compaction state, which was equivalent to an opening of time window for a normal cure cycle.

Fig. 1. Viscosity of 3501-6 Resin as a Function of Time

In order to measure the micro-structure development of the laminate, we had to know quantitatively the resin flow state of each individual ply. We impregnated very thin and porous teflon coated glass fabric sheets between plies. This made possible to measure the fiber volume fraction and resin content for each individual ply. The teflon coated glass fabric sheet (TCGF 400-2A) was made by American Durafilm Inc. The nominal thickness of the sheet was only about 0.025 mm (0.001 in). The porosity was over 60%, which was well beyond that of the fiber network, so that the flow field was undisturbed. This was verified by comparison of measurements of resin amount for specimens with and without impregnated teflon sheets. These teflon coated sheets made it possible to separate and measure the individual layers after the cure process.

A schematic of the laminate structure is shown in Fig. 2. The laminate consisted of 4 plies, 114 mm (4.5 in) by 102 mm (4 in), unidirectional. These dimensions were determined according to the available molding equipment and the consideration of dominant transverse flow, which limited the total layer number or the layer thickness otherwise the edge flow could not be neglected. The porous teflon coated sheets were cut in same size and impregnated during the

Fig. 2. Structure of the Laminate Test Specimen

lay-up operation. The thickness of the teflon coated sheets was on the order of the prepreg surface roughness so that careful lay-up operation can avoid trapping air. The laminate was surrounded by cork dams stuck on the bottom steel plate to prevent the resin flow within the prepreg ply plane. Bleeder paper was put on top of the laminate so that the resin flow was only in the upward direction. The top and bottom tool plates were used to conduct the heat and transfer the load to the laminate. The whole assembly was placed on a lab hot press, which was made by Carver Inc. The press was controlled by an IBM PC/XT computer and an ANDS 4400 data acquisition system made by Analogic Inc. Thermal couples were placed in the tool plates to monitor the temperature change. Pressure transducers were connected to the press hydraulic line to measure the load. The computer sent out the control signal via the data acquisition system to activate the heaters and the pressure pump, which realized the desired temperature and pressure cycle. The laminate structure was studied before and after the process. Since it is difficult to measure the prepreg thickness directly because of the surface property of the prepreg tape, each prepreg ply as well as teflon sheet and bleeder were all weighed before the cure cycle. The unique non-stick property of teflon coated sheets made it possible to separate each individual composite ply after the cure cycle. Then everything was weighed again to determine the resin content and fiber volume fraction of each ply. The formula used in the calculation was,

$$V_f = \frac{M_o V_o \rho_r}{M_o V_o (\rho_r - \rho_f) + M [(1 - V_o) \rho_r + V_o \rho_f]} \quad (1)$$

where V_f was the fiber volume fraction, ρ_f was the fiber density, ρ_r was the resin density, M_o was the original ply weight, and M was the final ply weight. The results of measured weight changes in all specimens showed that the bleeder absorbed over 90% percent of the resin flowing out of the composite. Therefore the flow process could be considered as one dimensional and in the upward direction only.

The selection of the pressure cycle was determined according to the viscosity curve. The heating rate of the hot press, which was set at the maximum heating rate, was about 11 °C/min (20 °F/min). Therefore the minimum resin viscosity point was reached after the heater was turned on about 12 to 13 minutes. The resin viscosity then increased rapidly and in a few minutes the resin was solidified. The pressure applied was very close to a step function of 1.4×10^7 Pa (20 psi) and was applied right after the low viscosity time period. The ideal pressure curve would be no pressure applied until the load was activated. In that way the initial fiber volume fraction, which was about 0.5, could be kept until the applied load was put on. However, in the experiments it was

necessary to apply a small pressure to close the mold for the heating process. This small pressure was only about 1.4×10^4 Pa (2 psi), which varied somewhat due to the friction of the press mechanisms. Since this pressure was applied from the beginning of the process, it was enough to press the fiber over the fiber volume fraction of about 0.55. There was no way to keep the laminate at the initial fiber volume fraction when the 1.4×10^5 Pa (20 psi) pressure was applied. This was included in the computer simulation to account for the first part of the flow process due to this small pressure. The applied temperature and pressure cycle was plotted in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Applied Temperature and Pressure Cycle

COMPUTER SIMULATION

The computer simulation was also performed and the results were compared with experiment measurements. The computer program was developed based on Gutowski's fiber deformation/resin flow model, which was discussed in detail in [4], in which the fiber network was treated as a nonlinear elastic porous medium and the resin flow was assumed to obey Darcy's law. To establish the physical model and mathematical equations, the coordinates of the laminate are chosen as shown in Fig. 4. For our bleeder molding case, we only considered the transverse resin flow and fiber movement. The continuity equation for this fiber and resin mixture is,

$$\frac{V_o^2}{V_f^2} \frac{\partial V_f}{\partial t} = - \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(\frac{V_f S_{zz}}{\mu} \frac{\partial P_r}{\partial z} \right) \quad (2)$$

where V_f is the fiber volume fraction, V_o is the initial fiber volume fraction and equal to 0.5, P_r is the resin pressure, μ is the resin viscosity, and S_{zz} is the permeability of the fiber network. This is a second order nonlinear diffusion equation with the unknowns V_f and P_r . The boundary conditions for this equation are that on top of the laminate, the resin pressure is equal to the atmospheric pressure, if we neglect the flow resistance of bleeder material, and at the bottom interface there is no flow.

Fig. 4. Coordinates of a Composite Laminate

The force balance condition is that the applied load is shared by the resin and the fiber,

$$P_a = P_r + \sigma_f \quad (3)$$

where P_a is the applied load and σ_f is the average fiber stress. The boundary conditions for equation (2) entered the calculation through this equation.

The permeability of the fiber bed in the transverse direction was found not constant and could be expressed as,

$$S_{zz} = \frac{r_f^2}{4K_z} \frac{\left(\frac{\sqrt{V_a'}}{\sqrt{V_f}} - 1\right)^3}{\frac{V_a'}{V_f} + 1} \quad (4)$$

where S_{zz} is the permeability, r_f is the fiber radius and equal to 0.004 mm, V_a' is the available fiber volume fraction for resin flow and is set to 0.8 according to the previous study, and K_z is the Kozeny constant which is equal to 0.2 from the experiment data fitting [1]. This equation was derived according to the original Carman-Kozeny equation but took into account the geometry of the transverse flow paths of the fiber network.

The deformation of the fiber network versus the transverse compression load can be written as,

$$\sigma_f = A_s \frac{\frac{\sqrt{V_f}}{\sqrt{V_o}} - 1}{\left(\frac{\sqrt{V_a'}}{\sqrt{V_f}} - 1\right)^4} \quad (5)$$

where σ_f is the average fiber stress (Pa or psi), V_o is the initial fiber volume fraction, V_a' is the available fiber volume fraction for fiber stress which is about 0.85 in most cases, and A_s is the spring constant and is equal to 4.1×10^2 Pa (0.06 psi) according to the experimental data fitting. This showed σ_f was a nonlinear function of V_f and the fiber stress increased rapidly when V_f became high.

Expression (4) and (5) are constitutive relations for the fiber network under the transverse compression load. The derivation and experiment verification of these relations were discussed in detail in [1].

The viscosity of the resin was calculated according to the expression given in [6], which was determined by the temperature cycle. The suggested expression was,

$$\mu = \mu_o \exp(U/RT + K\alpha) \quad (6)$$

where μ_o is a constant, U is the activation energy for viscosity, R is the universal gas constant, T is the absolute temperature, K is a constant independent of temperature, and α is the degree of cure. The data used here are all from [6] as follows: $\mu_o = 7.93 \times 10^{-14}$ PaSec, $K = 14.1$, $U = 9.08 \times 10^4$ J/mol. The calculation of α was also given in [6].

The numerical simulation program was written in FORTRAN on a micro VAX system. The experiment data of the pressure and temperature cycle were used as the input of the computer simulation program. The temperature distribution monitored by the thermal couples were used in the viscosity calculation. The fiber volume fraction and resin content were calculated as the program output and compared with the test results. The comparison of the data is shown in Fig. 5, in which the curve is the computer simulation output. The test data show good agreement with the computer output. The total amount of the resin flowing out from the laminate is consistent with the calculation based on the permeability relations (4). This verifies the Kozeny constant K_z obtained from the previous simulating experiments.

Fig. 5. Experiment Data and Computer Simulation Results

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The results of this experiment verifies the theoretical model and the proposed constitutive relations. The impregnation of the non-stick porous teflon coated glass fabric sheets and the selection of the special temperature and pressure cycle made it possible to monitor the resin flow and fiber motion during the laminate molding process.

The variation of the experiment data resulted from the process control and the rapidly changing viscosity of the resin. As the pressure was applied during the time period when the resin viscosity was increasing, the flow states could vary substantially even if there was only small time difference among different test runs.

The method of inserting porous and non-stick teflon coated glass fabric sheets was an effective way to measure the individual layer properties. This measuring method can be used to verify the resin flow models and to study the fiber distribution within the structure.

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